

Mercury Content of the Saltwater Fish from the Atlantic Ocean Coast of South Carolina

ANDREW K. KOLI, RONALD WHITMORE, WILLIAM CONYERS and KERWIN FELIX

Department of Natural Sciences, South Carolina State College, Orangeburg, South Carolina-29117

Manuscript received 2 May 1980, revised 15 December 1980, accepted 13 April 1981

A survey of mercury residues in saltwater fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina was conducted to see if the problem of the magnitude of mercury contamination was evident in the South Carolina fishery. Samples of saltwater fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected. Triplicate samples of fish tissue were analyzed by wet digestion method. Digests were analyzed using flameless atomic absorption spectrophotometry procedures outlined by Hatch and Ott as modified for use with a Perkin-Elmer, Coleman MAS-50 mercury analyzer. Different species vary in mercury content and larger fish contain higher concentrations of mercury than do smaller fish of the same species. All the fish analyzed contain mercury levels below the currently accepted guide line of 0.5 ppm. This means that fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina are relatively clean and safe with respect to mercury contamination for human consumption. Thus, the lower levels of mercury found in fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina can be related to less pollution due to exposure to waters from sewage, agricultural drainage, industrial waste and surface pollutants.

SOUTH Carolina State is a coastal plain country which has a long seacoast on the Atlantic Ocean.

There is no question that the seafood industry plays a large part in the economy of the state of South Carolina. More than enough seafood is caught offshore the South Carolina coast to meet the needs of South Carolinians. According to Dr. James Hite, a Clemson University Agriculture Agronomist, in 1971, South Carolinians consumed almost 24 million pounds of seafood. Dr. Hite says that in 1972 South Carolinians caught enough fish and shellfish from the sea to satisfy all their needs. But ecological, environmental and health problem pressures are being felt by the fishing industry. There has been no widespread, continued monitoring system of heavy metal uptake by fish or shellfish by any regulatory agencies, federal or local.

A survey of mercury residues in saltwater fish and shellfish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina was undertaken in September 1977. These investigations were initiated to determine mercury levels in fish and shellfish from South Carolina fishery. The survey was undertaken to see if the problem of the magnitude of mercury contamination was evident in the South Carolina fishery. Samples of saltwater fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected during 1977 and 1978. The species composition of the collections generally reflects the fish populations of the water sampled.

Many potentially dangerous chemicals ultimately find their way into waters which are natural habitats for fish. The fish which live in polluted water may accumulate pollutants from water via their food chains. Fish feeding on small marine organisms, on algae, on zooplankton, and on bottom sediments readily accumulate mercury. Since nutritionally and recreationally fish constitute a most important segment of the aquatic ecosystem, toxic metals in fish are obviously of great concern,

Experimental

Study Sites and Methods :

Sample collection : Samples of fish and shellfish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected during 1977 and 1978. The whole fresh fish were frozen on ice in an ice-chest and given an identification number, the date of collection, and the place of collection. The fish were then transported to the laboratory for weighing and storage. The whole fish were placed in plastic bags and stored in a freezer.

Wet digestion : Muscle tissue of fish, 0.2 g to 0.3 g was weighed accurately and placed in the bottom of a clean dry Erlenmeyer flask which is closed with a polyethylene stopper. And different tissues of Grouper have been analyzed. Samples were digested with 5 ml of 9M sulfuric acid and 1 ml of 5.6M nitric acid. The sample flasks were incubated in a shaking water bath at 58° until the tissue was completely dissolved giving a clear solution (50-60 minutes). Sample flasks were removed from the bath and allowed to cool in ice. Chemical oxidation of the samples were carried out by addition of 5 ml of 5% potassium permanganate slowly with swirling in each flask. Samples were kept overnight before analysis without apparent loss of mercury. Enough water was added to make the total volume approximately 100 ml. 1.5% hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution, 5 ml, was added to reduce the excess permanganate. After 30 seconds, 5 ml of 10% stannous chloride solution was added and immediately attached to the flask to the aeration system of mercury analyzer (Uthe *et al*, 1970).

Mercury determination by atomic absorption : Digests were analyzed using flameless atomic absorption spectrophotometry procedures outlined by Hatch and Ott¹, and Uthe *et al*² as modified for use with a Perkin Elmer, Coleman MAS-50 mercury

KOLI, WHITMORE, CONYERS & FELIX : MERCURY CONTENT OF THE SALTWATER FISH ETC.

TABLE 1—MERCURY LEVELS OF THE MUSCLE TISSUE OF SALTWATER FISH

Station	Date	Species	Weight in Grams	Mercury in Muscle ppm
Backman's Seafood Charleston	03/01/78	Whiting	294	0.12
	04/11/78	Spot	144.3	0.08
	04/13/78	Silver Snapper	1230	0.32
Beaufort	04/25/78	Flounder	240	0.41
	06/06/78	Shrimp	21.0	0.13
	06/06/78	Shrimp	13.0	0.03
	06/08/78	Shrimp	20.2	0.05
	06/08/78	Shrimp	19.1	0.05
	06/08/78	Shrimp	13.0	0.03
	06/15/78	Sea Bass	215.7	0.05
	06/15/78	Sea Bass	209.5	0.11
	06/15/78	Sea Bass	180.6	0.16
	06/15/78	Sea Bass	140.1	0.05
	06/19/78	Sea Bass	215.7	0.05
	06/19/78	Sea Bass	209.5	0.04
	06/19/78	Sea Bass	180.6	0.04
	06/19/78	Sea Bass	140.1	0.03
	06/22/78	Whiting	284.6	0.06
	06/22/78	Whiting	161.9	0.05
	06/22/78	Whiting	151.3	0.05
	06/22/78	Whiting	167.2	0.05
	06/26/78	Squid	181.9	0.05
	06/26/78	Squid	133.5	0.04
06/26/78	Whiting	250.1	0.07	
Charleston Fort Johnson	06/26/78	Whiting	193.5	0.05
	06/29/78	Snapper	1344	0.14
	06/29/78	Snapper	696.7	0.23
Beaufort	06/29/78	Grouper	365.9	0.12
	07/10/78	Whiting	284.6	0.18
	07/10/78	Whiting	161.9	0.19
	07/10/78	Whiting	151.3	0.19
Georgetown	07/10/78	Whiting	167.2	0.17
	07/10/78	Grouper	613.7	0.22
	07/10/78	Grouper	423.0	0.21
	07/10/78	Mullet	446.3	0.15
Hilton Head Is.	07/10/78	Mullet	292.6	0.17
	07/17/78	Bluefish	517.7	0.30
	07/17/78	Bluefish	404.3	0.16
	07/17/78	Grouper Fillet	744.5	0.52
Savannah	07/17/78	Dolphin Fillet	363.6	0.19
	07/24/78	Cod Fillet	620.4	0.22
	07/24/78	Clam	13.05	0.19
N. Myrtle Beach	07/24/78	Crab	171.1	0.20
	10/03/78	Scallop	5.00	0.23
	10/03/78	Scallop	5.50	0.30
Fort Johnson	10/19/78	Toad Fish	489	0.25
	10/19/78	Toad Fish	611.12	0.21
	10/24/78	Trinectes Maculatus	91.3	0.19
	10/24/78	Trinectes Maculatus	7.1	0.21
	10/24/78	Trinectes Maculatus	80.9	0.12
	10/30/78	Croacker	33.3	0.10
	10/30/78	Croacker	40.4	0.06
	10/30/78	Croacker	31.1	0.12
	11/02/78	Speckled Trout	325.3	0.12
	11/02/78	Spot	133.3	0.10
Georgetown	11/02/78	Spot	153.0	0.12
	11/02/78	Speckled Trout	370.0	0.12
	11/14/78	Spot	171.8	0.04
	11/14/78	Spot	156.9	0.05
	11/14/78	Spot	182.0	0.06
	11/14/78	Spot	141.7	0.07
	03/21/79	Rock Shrimp	10.9	0.13
	03/19/79	Sheephead	1560.8	0.12
N. Myrtle Beach	02/06/79	Scallop	5.2	0.15
Savannah, Georgia	02/06/79	Crab	112.5	0.29
Charleston	02/01/79	Flounder	287.0	0.17
Charleston	02/01/79	Spot	113.0	0.12
Myrtle Beach	01/31/79	Porgy (breem)	307.8	0.16
Myrtle Beach	01/25/79	Porgy	501.3	0.17
Myrtle Beach	01/25/79	Porgy	383.0	0.17
Hilton Head Is.	01/17/79	Dolphin	363.6	0.20
Myrtle Beach	01/17/79	Trout	863	0.14
Beaufort	06/08/79	Oyster	20.0	0.18

analyzer. Triplicate samples of fish tissue were analyzed by weight digestion method. Flameless atomic absorption method for determination of mercury is sensitive and rapid by reason of the very high absorbance at 253.7 nm of mercury vapor. Determination of mercury in fish muscle tissue was measured in parts per million (ppm). The analytical error was $\pm 10\%$ at 0.1 ppm mercury level.

Results and Discussion

Mercury determinations were made on 87 fish samples collected from eight locations on the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina (Tables 1 and 2). The species composition of the collections generally reflects the fish populations of the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina. The whole body weight of fish collected varied from 1554g to 7.1g with an average of 482 g (Table 1). All species of fish collected and analyzed contain mercury. Mercury levels in fish averaged 0.14 ppm and ranged between 0.52 ppm and 0.03 ppm (Table 1). Different species vary in mercury content and larger fish contain high concentrations of mercury than do smaller fish of the same species (Table 1).

TABLE 2—MERCURY LEVELS OF THE DIFFERENT TISSUES OF GROUPEL*

Organ Tissue	Mercury Levels ppm
Muscle	0.12
Liver	0.24
Kidney	0.15
Heart	0.19
Brain	0.25
Spleen	0.17
Skin	0.12
Scale	0.15
Gill	0.12
Bone	0.24
Fin	0.13
Eye	0.13
Tongue	0.14
Stomach	0.15

* Grouper weighing 1564 grams was collected from station Fort Johnson on July 6, 1978.

Mercury levels exceeding the U. S. Food and Drug Administration Guideline of 0.5 ppm for muscle tissue have only been found in Grouper Fillet (Table 1). No other fish had found mercury levels above the currently accepted guideline of 0.5 ppm (Table 1). This is a good indication that fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina are relatively clean and safe with respect to mercury for human consumption. Thus, the lower levels of mercury found in fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina can be related to less pollution due to exposure to waters from sewage, agricultural drainage, industrial waste, and surface pollutants.

Our results were compared with already published data from investigations of mercury pollution in the aquatic environment of the South-Eastern United States^{3,4,5,6}. The results were consistent with the published data.

Acknowledgement

This work is a result of a research grant supported by CSRS Grant No. 701-15-08A, U. S. Department of Agriculture, in cooperation with Cooperative State Research Service, USDA. The authors thank Dr. H. L. Hauser, Associate 1890 Research Director, and Dr. J. H. Arrington, Chairman of the Natural Sciences Department of their efforts in this research.

References

1. W. R. HATCH and W. L. OTT, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 2085.
2. J. F. UTHE, F. A. J. ARMSTRONG and M. P. STANTON, *J. Fish. Res. Bd. Canada*, 1970, **27**, 805.
3. H. D. ZELLER and J. H. FINGER, Tenth Annual Environmental and Water Resources Engineering Conference, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, Tennessee, 1971.
4. S. JENSEN and A. JERNBELOV, *Nature*, 1969, **223**, 753.
5. A. K. KOLI, W. R. WILLIAMS, E. B. MCCLARY, E. L. WRIGHT and T. M. BURRELL, *Bull. Environ. Cont. and Tox.*, 1977, **17**, 82.
6. K. MATSUNAGA, *Nature*, 1975, **257**, 49.